

How can Pacific small island developing states (SIDS) resist digital colonialism?

“But we know well that this is the greatest taboo all over the world, that is, to leave behind the so-called Western civilization, because it means leaving patriarchy as such behind. This rupture is almost unimaginable anywhere, except within the indigenous worlds” (Escobar, 2018).

ABSTRACT

The internet is a pervasive reality yet it’s hard to conceive that it is a created construct with only three decades of the global interconnected web (Roser et al., 2015). By 2018, half the worldwide population were online, on reaching such a critical mass, one asks the question who is it for? This essay argues that the design of the infrastructure of internet and its exploitation is a new kind of power coloniality called digital colonialism (Andres Guadamuz, 2017). I explore unique challenges for Pacific small island states (SIDS) and explore the infrastructure design issues in the face of current pressures for large scale digitalisation policies (Diamana, 2015; Filho et al., 2021; Rossignol, 2014).

1. INTRODUCTION and LITERATURE REVIEW

The internet (specifically, the world wide web) is a created construct that has been consciously designed by designers (the Guardian, 2017). Now that the internet has matured its infrastructure, created standardised processes and achieved global penetration, it is re-producing power systems in ‘real’ life; there is an emerging body of literature which is witnessing a new manifestation of power coloniality - digital colonialism (Kwet, 2019).

Digital colonialism is manifestation of a new form of coloniality of power which uses the ‘means of coloniality’ from historic colonialism, which involved (Europeans) dispossessing native people of their lands, taking control, exploiting their labour and extracting resources from the periphery (sites of colonisation) to the centre (sites of colonisers) (Cowen, 2020). We are interested in the legacies of colonialism that is sustained, which can be classified into three types: systems of knowledge, system of hierarchies and cultural systems (Quijano and Ennis, 2000; Quijano, 2007). Intersecting these systems are tools/means of coloniality, these can also be summarised into three key concepts: extraction, superiority and control (Arora et al., 2020).

The Commonwealth (2014) has announced research in Pacific Small Island Developing States (SIDS) and their suitability for digital industrialisation for economic growth. Implementation of digital architecture in the context of Small Island Developing States (SIDS) is an emerging research area for academics (University of Cambridge, 2021), international organisations (UN and related agencies, Commonwealth Secretariat), private consulting firms (PwC (2021), McKinsey (2021), GSMA (2021)) and individual states looking to develop, monitor and evaluate national industrial policies (Japan and Korea). However, there are significant gaps, for instance, there are no published research papers on this topic specific to Pacific SIDS, thus, this essay contributes to this discussion (Goundar et al., 2020).

2. ANALYSIS

Development of digital policies for Pacific Small Island Developing States (SIDS)

Pacific Small Island Developing States (SIDS) are a special group of countries that have unique challenges (dispersed small population, 'simple' national economic structures, unfeasible economic trade routes etc.), see figure below for a selected Pacific countries (Farrugia, 2007).

Figure 1: Visual of selected Pacific Small Island Developing States (SIDS). Adapted from the Guardian (Nicholas et al., 2021).

The premise by development policy advisors is that countries that were traditionally constrained by small, dispersed, unconnected population such as landlocked Africa or Small Island Developing States (SIDS) can leverage the potential of digital infrastructure (Lin et al., 2017).

Mauritius (Government of Mauritius, 2021), an Island in Southern Africa, is a good case study for one of the most comprehensive e-government policies (they are digitising almost every domain of governmentality (Scott, 1998) e.g., e-courts, e-business, e-citizenship etc.). Moreover, for industrialising economies, it need not take centuries to 'catchup', China has demonstrated that within decades, focussed investment policies can lead to emerging as the superpower in 5G and AI technologies (Li et al., 2020).

In the next five years, Industry 4.0 (fourth industrial revolution) is expected to grow by a factor of ten from \$350 billion to \$3.2 trillion (Asian Development Bank, 2020). Small Island Developing States (SIDS) could position themselves to capture a small slice of a very large pie in years to come, but this will require strategic focus on niche areas responding to unique challenges of SIDS but also preserving their local/regional way of life.

Current state of play

Currently, internet access for Pacific SIDS inhabitants is clustered around low connectivity, with a few states such as Tuvalu and Nauru having higher fixed broadband and Fiji have much larger mobile broadband coverage. The economic value of mobile operations in Pacific Islands is \$1.22 billion (GSMA, 2021) and it is likely to grow further. In terms of the desired state, most Pacific SIDS would like to see increased intensity of existing infrastructure, increased resilience (redundancy) by investing in both mobile and broadband capabilities and a regional approach to protect value chains from being captured outside of the Pacific region (UN, 2021). Thus, the policy options are currently framed as a feasibility for low-cost internet enabling technologies and architecture and support for MSMEs as telecoms service provider. However, in the next session we will explore the wider implications of adopting 'free' access to internet infrastructure.

Figure 2: Internet connectivity for Pacific SIDS. Source: (UNESCAP, 2021).

3. DISCUSSION

There's no such thing as a free lunch: Facebook, one of the largest social media conglomerates in the world has been accused of digital colonialism (the Guardian, 2017) on its 'Free Basics' service – a firewall of limited internet for poor countries. The 'free' service takes up prominent digital real estate space for US private companies such as Johnson and Johnson – this crowds out local operators, thus, 'free' services are used in a 'freemium' model to wean users into extractive processes whereby extra-territorial firms are able to capture and profit off user data. Global Voices (the Guardian, 2017) say that “the program has created substantial new avenues for Facebook to gather data about the habits and interests of users in countries where they aspire to have a strong presence, as more users come online”.

Similarly, Google ventured to provide free internet access and connect remote communities across Africa using weather balloon like technology called Loon, this too was met with critique due to data sovereignty concerns, and ultimately wound down at the end of 2017 (Andres Guadamuz, 2017).

The key things for Pacific SIDS to draw lessons is that blanket access to free internet has strings attached. One organisation that has been leading the charge in championing more diverse, inclusive and open internet for the global community is the not-for-profit Mozilla Foundation. To cite an example, MozFest (2021) organises workshops across the world to raise awareness of data privacy and rights ceded by users. In their 'ethical café' scenario, they allow users to access freebies (e.g., buying ice cream) but they need to accept the terms of the End User Agreement License (EUAL). Would you grab that free ice cream after reading the below notice?

Figure 3: MozFest ethical cafe - demonstration of End User License Agreement in practical real-world example e.g., getting an ice cream for free but having to accept all these terms. Source: (MozFest, 2021)

Money is available but needs to be accessed without strings attached: donors are invested in the Pacific SIDS, as this block has emerged as a stronger political group (Pacific SIDS Forum), they also represent 20% of the UN membership which allows them to be courted by both China and USA, moreover, they have substantial natural resources which unfortunately are captured outside the region (Goundar et al., 2020). There are indeed quick wins for digital investment e.g., protecting the 530K tonnes of seafood products (\$1.2bn) against illegal fishing practice by large Chinese sea boats (Field, 2021). Additionally, by investing in high tech digital sensors Pacific SIDS will be able to track fishing movement in response to warming water temperatures. Thus, Pacific SIDS can reorient donor, trade and capital investments towards sovereign digital infrastructure.

Designing for plurality: finally, what's missing from this debate is who is the internet for? It is evident that early adopters such as European and North American states (Roser et al., 2015) were first movers and have now dominated the inter-net(work) with the same power coloniality preceding it. Thus, we need a framework to pluralise this network to allow other worlds to exist, specifically, indigenous cultures. Escobar (2018) argues that "design is too important to be left to designers", instead, we need to take a multi-disciplinary approach to designing for pluriverse – 'a world where many worlds fit' (Escobar, 2017). To do this, we need to move away from patriarchal systems towards matriarchal systems.

Patriarchal features are embedded within power coloniality as manifested in the modern world; the other side of the spectrum is matriarchal systems. In Designing for the pluriverse, Escobar (2018) argues that indigenous communities are more likely to be matriarchal, they are less likely to see the world as delineated subject-object relationship to be controlled, instead, there is a relationship between the both human and non-human world, in that we share consciousness and subjectivity. Therefore, we move towards **Care** and **Conviviality**, where we refuse to treat non-human being as objects (care) and work towards co-existence for all worlds (conviviality) (Arora et al., 2020).

Another feature of modern design values is that they have a 'de-futuring' effect, meaning they create 'structured unsustainability' whereby non-modern cultures cease to survive within this hegemonic Design paradigm. Instead, we need to move towards speculative design – a relationship way of being with the world informed by critical design theory which looks at the world as not things are but what the alternative could be. In this way, they attempt to diversify Designs for the 'multiverse of worlds our worlds could be' (Escobar, 2018).

Recognition: United Nations Environment Programme (2015) now recognise the value of indigenous knowledge systems in Pacific SIDS for their role in disaster management, although there is recognition of its existence there is currently little body of published knowledge on this. The policy recommendation is to initiate processes to record such knowledge bases before they cease to exist, whilst laudable, to what extent would the digitisation of such knowledge further contribute to knowledge appropriate of indigenous cultures where the capital accumulation is captured elsewhere?

4. CONCLUSION

The key assertion of this essay is that historic colonialism (Europeans and age of discovery into Latin America) led to systems of power coloniality which involved processes of control, extractivism and superiority, these are now inherent within modernity and no longer exclusive to European historical processes.

The next decades will be defined by hyperconnectivity of the internet (Industry 4.0), this will pervade almost all aspects of life and will replicate power coloniality. Therefore, all states, not just developing states, need to be cognizant of the power being accumulated by global data extractivists, who are no longer nation states, instead large corporations like Facebook and Google.

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